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Guidelines and Codes on the participation of indigenous peoples and local communities of the Convention on Biological Diversity: A comparative analysis using natural language processing

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1. Introduction

This working paper introduces some results from a method of comparative linguistic analysis applied to legal texts. The method can be used for large amounts of legal text, but relies on deep researcher knowledge for the interpretation of results and, crucially, the specification of the method. This method was developed within the BENELEX project on benefit-sharing and the role of law with a view to building on previous discourse and frame analyses of decisions of the Convention on Biological Diversity's (CBD) Conference of Parties (COP).¹ These more manual analyses focused only on those decisions discussing indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLCs), with the aim of mapping discourses about these groups as well as meanings and mechanisms for participation. To widen this type of analysis to include the whole texts of COP decisions, a methodology employing automated text analysis was needed. The eventual aim for the method outlined here is thus to extend linguistic analysis to the entire corpus of COP decision texts. This will facilitate comparisons between discourses focusing on indigenous peoples and local communities, already identified using more manual techniques, with those that are used to refer to other actors and particularly the private sector. This paper presents work completed so far on the specification of the method and a first 'test' application to three CBD documents relating to the traditional knowledge and participation of indigenous peoples and local communities.² These are i) the Akwé: Kon Guidelines;³ the Tkarihawaié:ri Code of Ethical Conduct;⁴ and the Mo'otz Kuxtal Voluntary Guidelines.⁵

This work was undertaken under the auspices of the five-year (2013-2018) European Research Council funded BENELEX project.⁶ The project aimed to investigate both the conceptual and practical dimensions of the legal concept of fair and equitable benefit sharing. This included its 'role and limitations in ensuring fairness and equity in the identification and allocation among different stakeholders of the advantages arising from environmental protection, the sustainable use of natural resources, and the production of knowledge.'⁷

¹ L Parks, 'Spaces for local voices? A discourse analysis of the decisions of the Convention on Biological Diversity' 9 *Journal of Human Rights and the Environment* (2018) 141-170; L Parks & M Schroeder 'What we talk about when we talk about 'local' participation in international biodiversity law. The changing scope of Indigenous peoples and local communities' participation under the Convention on Biological Diversity' 11 *Participation and Conflict* (2018) 743-785.

² Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), 1992, 1760 UNTS 79.

³ Akwé: Kon Voluntary Guidelines for the Conduct of Cultural, Environmental and Social Impact Assessment Regarding Developments Proposed to Take Place on, or which are Likely to Impact on, Sacred Sites and on Lands and Waters traditionally Occupied or Used by Indigenous and Local Communities, CBD Decision VII/16, Annex, Montreal (2004).

⁴ Tkarihawaié:ri Code of Ethical Conduct on Respect for the Cultural and Intellectual Heritage of Indigenous and Local Communities, CBD Decision X/42, Annex, Montreal (2010).

⁵ Mo'otz kuxtal Voluntary Guidelines for the development of mechanisms, legislation or other appropriate initiatives to ensure the 'prior and informed consent', 'free, prior and informed consent' or 'approval and involvement', depending on national circumstances, of indigenous peoples and local communities for accessing their knowledge, innovations and practices, for fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of their knowledge, innovations and practices relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and for reporting and preventing unlawful appropriation of traditional knowledge, CBD/COP/DEC/XIII/18, Annex, Montreal, (2016).

⁶ See: The BENELEX Project Website:

<https://www.strath.ac.uk/research/strathclydecentreenvironmentallawgovernance/BENELEXBENELEX/>

⁷ BENELEX Project Report 2015-2018 (2019) at 2.

Along with seeking to better understand the progressive development of this concept, the BENELEX project attempted to ‘identify challenges for [IPLCs] in fairly and equitably sharing benefits in different sectors in different regions in the world, and the interface between local, national, regional and international law in this connection.’⁸ One of the questions identified during the project was about the forms of IPLC participation envisaged in CBD decisions – this was the driving force being the research undertaken in this paper.

The analysis of these three documents, well known by the members of the BENELEX research team, is intended to act as a ‘test’ of the method, since the results can be judged on the basis of in-depth knowledge. Beyond this ‘test’, the purpose of the comparative study is to map the evolution of language used towards the participation of IPLCs in the CBD arena, focusing on patterns over time that may not come to the fore via fine-grained legal analyses.

However, such fine-grained analysis is close to impossible using conventional doctrinal methods. By using natural language processing (NLP) in the analysis of these CBD Guidelines and Codes, we can track the evolution of terms in order to answer the following research questions:

- Has the language used towards the participation of IPLCs in comparison with other actors, evolved over time?
- What terms have appeared, disappeared, or reappeared over time within the COP decisions, and why?

The decision to focus on these three documents as a small-scale comparative test case was also driven by the previous analyses. Parks’ initial work sought to investigate if discursive space for “commons and other community driven approaches to the conservation of natural resources at the global level of environmental governance” existed within the context of the CBD.⁹ The analysis challenged the claims found in some literature about a lack of spaces where local voices and approaches are taken seriously in global arenas. One of the most frequent discourses concerning IPLCs that came from this analysis was “participation” thereby warranting further research into the levels of participation outlined in CBD COP decisions.

Parks & Schröder’s further work was a more refined discourse analysis of coded sections of CBD COP decisions that related solely to IPLCs participation. Over the course of thirteen COP Decisions analysed, one of the main findings was that there was a “peak” in discussion on participation in COP 7, when the Akwé: Kon Guidelines were adopted. This merits further study of the Tkarihawié:ri Code and the Mo’otz Kuxtal Voluntary Guidelines as these related to participation of IPLCs and were adopted in 2010 and 2013 respectively.

This paper begins by outlining the object and purpose of each of the three Guidelines and Codes and what they mean in legal terms, including a discussion on whether such documents are binding or non-binding in nature (with a particular focus on the Akwé: Kon Guidelines).

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ L Parks “Space for Local Voices” (2018) at 27.

We then present preliminary notes on the evolution of the language structure between the three documents analysed.

2. Akwé: Kon Voluntary Guidelines (CBD Decision VII/16)

The CBD Conference of Parties (COP) 7 in Kuala Lumpur in 2004 saw the adoption of the Akwé: Kon Voluntary Guidelines. The Guidelines provide comprehensive and systematic guidance on the conduct of prior environmental and socio-cultural impact assessment (ESCIA); and are viewed as a crucial instrument with regards to the development and implementation of Article 8(j) of the CBD which concerns traditional knowledge, innovations, and practices in the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity.¹⁰

The Guidelines provide general advice on incorporation of indigenous considerations.¹¹ Including clarification “processes should be established for recording indigenous communities; views, including when they are unable to attend public meetings because of remoteness or poor health, as well as in forms other than written ones.”¹² The purpose of the Guidelines is to provide a collaborative framework for governments, IPLCs, private developers and decision makers to support full and effective participation and involvement of IPLCs, thereby identifying and implementing appropriate measures to prevent or mitigate any negative impacts of proposed developments on IPLCs’ traditional or sacred lands and waters.¹³

The Guidelines are to be implemented at the national level by proponents of policies and projects and are based on the Integrated Environmental Assessment (IEA) principle¹⁴ divided into four main stages: preparatory, main, reporting & decision making; and monitoring & auditing.¹⁵ There are also numerous other possible stages that may be followed when undertaking an impact assessment, including notification of and public consultation on proposed developments.¹⁶

¹⁰ CBD, Art. 8(j) states: ‘Each contracting Party shall, as far as possible and as appropriate: Subject to national legislation, respect, preserve and maintain knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities embodying traditional lifestyles relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity and promote their wider application with the approval and involvement of the holders of such knowledge, innovations and practices and encourage the equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the utilization of such knowledge innovations and practices.’ See also M Fitzmaurice ‘The dilemma of traditional knowledge: Indigenous peoples and traditional knowledge’ *International Community Law Review* 10 (2008) 255-278 at 262.

¹¹ Akwé: Kon Guidelines, Para. 2.

¹² E Morgera, ‘Dawn of a new day? The evolving relationship between the convention on biological diversity and international human rights law’ *Wake Forest Law Review* 54 (In Press) at 111; Akwé: Kon Guidelines, Para. 17.

¹⁴ Defined by the European Environmental Agency (EEA) as “the interdisciplinary process of identification, analysis and appraisal of all relevant natural and human processes and their integrations which determine both the current and future state of environmental quality, and resources, on appropriate spatial and temporal scales, thus facilitating the framing and implementation of policies and strategies.” See L S Anderson, C E Davies and D Moss (1997) ‘The UN Convention on Biological Diversity - Follow-up in EEA Member Countries 1996’ (Online) <<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/92-9167-077-4>> Annex I.

¹⁵ Akwé: Kon, para. 7

¹⁶ Akwé: Kon, para. 8

Public participation is strongly rooted in the Akwé: Kon Guidelines, which “is envisaged as enabling the identification of including indigenous and local communities and stakeholders likely affected by the proposed activities”¹⁷ The Guidelines acknowledge the “unique relationship between indigenous and local communities and the environment” and allow for the consideration of cultural, environmental and social impact assessments as one holistic process.¹⁸ A list of general considerations is given when carrying out impact assessment including prior informed consent and gender considerations.¹⁹ Governments should also provide adequate resources (human, financial, technical and legal) to support IPLC expertise and facilitate effective participation in the impact assessment process.²⁰ The Akwé: Kon Guidelines can be said to further develop Article 8(j) with a focus on public participation and broad consideration to the interests of IPLCs, women, and other actors.

The Akwé: Kon Guidelines “can play an important role in inspiring national implementation and impact assessments, especially to measure impacts on Indigenous Peoples”²¹ As they are not binding on States *per se* (paragraph 1 of the Guidelines explicitly states they are voluntary in character), Fitzmaurice stresses the “soft law” nature of the Akwé: Kon Guidelines, noting their voluntary character and arguing their application relies on States’ goodwill.²² But it is important to note that the Guidelines were accepted by consensus by Parties to the CBD,²³ which is one of the widest ratified multilateral treaties in existence, with 196 parties. In addition, decisions by the Inter-American Court of Human Rights and the reports of UN Special Rapporteurs,²⁴ have referred to the Akwé: Kon Guidelines and other CBD guidelines.²⁵ This indicates that CBD guidelines can be considered authoritative aids to interpretation of legally binding instruments or at least best practice, as discussed in greater depth in other BENELEX research.²⁶

3. The Tkarihwaí:ri Code of Ethical Conduct (CBD Decision X/42)

¹⁷ Fitzmaurice at 263.

¹⁸ Akwé: Kon Guidelines, para. 23.

¹⁹ *Ibid.* Para. 3.

²⁰ *Ibid.* Para. 18.

²¹ E Morgera & J Razzaque at 269.

²² Fitzmaurice at 264.

²³ CBD Decision VII/16 F.

²⁴ J Anaya (Special Rapporteur on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples), *Measures Needed to Secure Indigenous and Tribal Peoples’ Land and Related Rights in Suriname*, paras. 8-12 UN Doc A/HRC/18/15/add.7 (Aug. 18, 2011); E Morgera, ‘The legacy of UN Special Rapporteur Anaya on Indigenous Peoples and Benefit-Sharing’, BeneLex Blog, (May 29, 2014), < <https://benelexblog.wordpress.com/2014/05/29/the-legacy-of-un-special-rapporteur-anaya-on-indigenous-peoples-and-benefit-sharing/>>; J Knox (Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and the Environment), *Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Issue of Human Rights Obligations Relating to the Enjoyment of a Safe, Clean, Healthy and Sustainable Environment*, paras 47-53, UN Doc A/HRC/34/49 (Jan 19, 2017).

²⁵ IAcHR, *case of the Saramaka People v. Suriname. Interpretation of the Judgements of Preliminary Objections, Merits, Reparations and Costs*. Judgement of August 12, 2008. Series C No. 185. Para. 41; IAcHR, *Case of Kaliña and Lokono Peoples v Suriname*, Judgment (Merits, Reparations and Costs), 25 November 2015; IAcHR, *Comunidad Garífuna Triunfo de la Cruz y Sus Miembros vs Honduras* (Merits, Reparations and Costs), 8 October 2015; IAcHR, *Comunidad Garífuna de Punta Piedra y Sus Miembros vs Honduras* (Preliminary Exceptions, Merits, Reparations and Costs), 8 October 2015

²⁶ E Morgera, ‘Under the radar: The role of fair and equitable benefit-sharing in protecting and realizing human rights connected to natural resources’ BENELEX Working Paper N. 10 (rev October 2010); E Morgera, ‘Dawn of a new day? The evolving relationship between the convention on biological diversity and international human rights law’ *Wake Forest Law Review* 54 (In Press) at 107-8, 114-15.

At the CBD COP 10 in 2010, the Tkarihwaí:ri Code of Ethical Conduct to Ensure Respect for the Cultural and Intellectual Heritage of Indigenous and Local Communities Relevant to the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Biological Diversity was adopted by the CBD Parties.²⁷

Focusing mainly on cultural heritage and intellectual property of IPLCs, the Code intends to give guidance regarding activities and interactions with IPLCs and for the development of local, national, or regional codes of ethical conduct. These should, in line with Article 8(j) of the CBD, aim to promote respect, maintenance and preservation of traditional knowledge, innovations and practices relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. The Code “underscores that to respect traditional knowledge requires valuing equally with, and complimentary to, scientific knowledge, in order to promote the full respect for the cultural and intellectual heritage of indigenous and local communities relevant to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.”²⁸

The Code provides, *inter alia*, for recognition of sacred sites and lands traditionally occupied by IPLCs,²⁹ and transparency/full disclosure,³⁰ as well as prior and informed consent and/or approval and involvement on activities that may affect these areas.³¹ The Code therefore complements the Akwé: Kon Guidelines, by indicating frameworks should be developed for activities on lands and waters traditionally occupied by IPLCs, and that IPLCs should be enabled to promote respect of their traditional knowledge and associated biological and genetic resources.

Morgera notes the purpose of the Code’s development was “to address other key concerns for [IPLCs] in regard to research on their knowledge and other activities which have in some cases resulted in misappropriation of their knowledge and other activities which have had negative impacts on their way of life and cultural and intellectual heritage.”³² Aimed at promoting respect for the cultural and intellectual heritage of IPLCs where it is relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, the Code provides guidance in establishing or improving national frameworks for activities or interactions with IPLCs.

The Code not only provide guidance to CBD Parties and governments, it is also aimed at other actors that work with IPLCs such as research and educational institutions. It is important to note that the Code contains ethical principles, which is interesting as this term is not used elsewhere in other CBD instruments. In the context of research, the term ‘ethics’ is common and refers to the fact that interpretations may differ between those conducting the research and those IPLCs who are participating in, or being subjected to research.³³

Ethical guidelines for research generally are commonplace and, in this case, exist in The Tkarihwaí:ri Code to prevent misappropriation of traditional knowledge and to set out stronger and more detailed principles to carry out such research. This includes general

²⁷ “Tkarihwaí:ri” Is a Mohawk term meaning “the proper way” was provided by the Elders of the Mohawk Community of Kahnawake. The Mohawk are the traditional custodians of the area of Montreal where the code was negotiated. Source: CBD website: <https://www.cbd.int/traditional/code.shtml>

²⁸ E Morgera, ‘Fair and equitable benefit-sharing at the cross-roads of the human right to science and international biodiversity law’ *Laws* 4 (2015) 803-831 at 820.

²⁹ *Ibid.* Art 17.

³⁰ *Ibid.* Art. 10.

³¹ *Ibid.* Arts. 10-11.

³² E Morgera & J Razzaque at 270.

³³ E.g. L Tuhiwai Smith, *Decolonizing Methodologies* (Zed Books, 2012).

principles on prior informed consent and fair and equitable benefit sharing, as well as the methods to achieve them “such as respecting indigenous decision-making structures and full and effective participation of IPLCs in all activities related to biodiversity conservation and its use.”³⁴ Article 4 touches on the issue of identification of relevant knowledge holders, based on indigenous laws, and recognises that the rights and authority are sat with respective peoples or communities.³⁵

The Code is voluntary, and explicitly states its purpose is not to ‘interpret the obligations of the CBD.’³⁶ In comparison to the discussion on the Akwé: Kon Guidelines above, the Code is yet to be cited by any international, regional or national courts.

4. Mo’otz Kuxtal Voluntary Guidelines

The Mo’otz Kuxtal Voluntary Guidelines were adopted at COP 13 in Cancún, Mexico in 2016.³⁷ In comparison to the guidelines discussed above, the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines adopt the term IPLC for the first time,³⁸ and address three issues around the use of IPLC traditional knowledge – namely that i) IPLCs should receive fair and equitable benefits based on mutually agreed terms from use of their traditional knowledge,³⁹ ii) Tools and mechanisms should be established for the prevention and reporting of unlawful appropriation and use of traditional knowledge; and iii) Access to traditional knowledge. The Guidelines require governments to develop mechanisms, legislation or other initiative as appropriate to ensure, depending on national circumstances, a form of “prior and informed consent” is achieved. In addition, the Guidelines highlight the importance of customary laws and ‘community protocols’ These two points are discussed in more detail below.

4.1 Free and Prior Informed Consent (FPIC)

“Free and prior informed consent” (FPIC) is referred to in the full title of the Guidelines in two other formulations: “prior and informed consent” and “approval and involvement.” These multiple formulations indicate a lack of consensus between CBD Parties.⁴⁰ This is understood as “the reluctance by some CBD Parties to fully endorse the standards enshrined in UNDRIP”⁴¹ as many Parties to the CBD are not party to the UNDRIP regime and do not wish to implement those international standards on IPLCs “through the backdoor of the CBD.”⁴²

³⁴ E Morgera & J Razzaque at 270; See: Tkarihwaié:ri Code. arts. 27 and 30.

³⁵ *Ibid.* art. 4; See Also E Morgera & J Razzaque (eds.) *Biodiversity and Nature Protection Law* 270.

³⁶ *Ibid.* paras. 14 and 1.

³⁷ Mo’otz kuxtal Voluntary Guidelines for the development of mechanisms, legislation or other appropriate initiatives to ensure the ‘prior and informed consent’, ‘free, prior and informed consent’ or ‘approval and involvement’, depending on national circumstances, of indigenous peoples and local communities for accessing their knowledge, innovations and practices, for fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of their knowledge, innovations and practices relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and for reporting and preventing unlawful appropriation of traditional knowledge, CBD/COP/DEC/XIII/18 (2016); “Mo’otz Kuxtal” means “roots of life” in the Maya language.

³⁸ In line with CBD Decision XII/12 F, paras. 2(a-c).

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⁴⁰ Note that FPIC is also found in Art. 7 of the Nagoya Protocol.

⁴¹ E Morgera, ‘Under the radar: The role of fair and equitable benefit-sharing in protecting and realizing human rights connected to natural resources’ BENELEX Working Paper N. 10 (rev October 2010) at 20.

⁴² *Ibid* at 9.

Multiple IPLC representatives at the CBD Article 8(j) Working Group discussing the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines prior to its adoption had stressed the word 'free' was necessary for inclusion. This was due to additional implied content beyond the meaning of not being coerced: IPLCs were concerned about being free in setting the terms of the decision-making process. For example, IPLC representatives suggested that they should be free in setting the timing, language and information provisions of decision-making.⁴³

Morgera notes that during the heated negotiations of the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines at COP 13, the draft included a large quantity of suggestions made by IPLC representatives, and the subject of FPIC was the most contentious.⁴⁴ Eventually, three different standards of protection are included in the Guidelines, which state it is not practical to propose a "one size fits all" approach and recommend "taking into account national and local circumstances of the indigenous peoples and local communities concerned."⁴⁵ Indeed, FPIC is to be applied "subject to national legislation," which gives States a wide discretion in its application.⁴⁶ The Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines, nevertheless, explains that [FPIC] has a number of connotations,⁴⁷ as follows:

- *Free* should be understood that IPLCs should not be "pressured, intimidated, manipulated or unduly influenced" on top of absence of coercion;⁴⁸ No reference to time-scale for IPLCs to make a decision is included here, as intended by IPLC representatives.
- *Prior* recalls the need to seek consent or approval for access to traditional knowledge;⁴⁹
- *Informed* indicates that information that covers relevant aspects of the activity;⁵⁰
- *Consent or approval* means the right to refuse consent or approval, only permits temporary use of traditional knowledge for the purpose for which it was granted;⁵¹
- What *consent or approval* should be made up of includes: written application in a manner and language comprehensible to the traditional knowledge holder; a

⁴³ See Blog Post by E Morgera 'Assessing the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines on benefit sharing from the use of traditional knowledge' (2017) Online at: <https://BeneLexBeneLexblog.wordpress.com/2017/03/01/reflections-on-2016-un-biodiversity-conference-part-ii-assessing-the-mootz-kuxtal-guidelines-on-benefit-sharing-from-the-use-of-traditional-knowledge/> (Last Checked 20/08/18).

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*

⁴⁵ Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines, Para. 9.

⁴⁶ CBD Article 8(j); Nagoya Protocol, Art. 6(2).

⁴⁷ Blog Post by E Morgera 'Assessing the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines on benefit sharing from the use of traditional knowledge' (2017) Online at: <https://BeneLexBeneLexblog.wordpress.com/2017/03/01/reflections-on-2016-un-biodiversity-conference-part-ii-assessing-the-mootz-kuxtal-guidelines-on-benefit-sharing-from-the-use-of-traditional-knowledge/> (Last Checked 20/08/18).

⁴⁸ Mo'otz Kuxtal, Para. 7(a).

⁴⁹ Mo'otz Kuxtal, Para. 7(b).

⁵⁰ *Ibid.* para. 7(c).

⁵¹ *Ibid.* para. 7(d).

legitimate and culturally appropriate form of process and decision-making, including consideration of possible social, cultural and economic impacts; adequate and balanced information from a variety of sources that is made available in indigenous or local languages using terms understood by indigenous peoples and local communities, and including safeguards to ensure that all parties to an agreement have the same understanding of the information and terms provided; and culturally appropriate timing and deadlines;⁵²

- *Consent or approval* should be a “continual process of building mutually beneficial, ongoing arrangements between users and holders of traditional knowledge ongoing arrangements between users and holders of traditional knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities, in order to build trust, good relations, mutual understanding, intercultural spaces, knowledge exchanges, create new knowledge and reconciliation”⁵³ This indicates that consent or approval as a process is iterative, and not a one-off exercise and should “underpin and be an integral part of developing a relationship between users and provided of traditional knowledge”⁵⁴

Morgera argues that the above indications are:

[H]elpful to clarify the international community’s expectations about the quality and fundamental aims of interactions between governments and non-state actors and [IPLCs]. To a significant extent, they support the aim of [IPLCs] representatives engaging in CBD processes, who have argued that ‘free’ serves to imply a process that is self-directed by the community’ from whom consent is sought with a view to emphasising the need for communities to control the context of decision-making.⁵⁵

4.2 Community Protocols

The Guidelines highlight the importance of customary laws and ‘community protocols’ defined as “a broad array of expressions, articulations, rules and practices generated by communities to set out how they expect other stakeholders to engage with them.”⁵⁶ Community protocols have been referred to explicitly in the Nagoya Protocol,⁵⁷ and can be considered as a recurring feature in work relating to traditional knowledge under the CBD. The Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines are helpful in providing an understanding of what community protocols are. The Guidelines indicated the benefits for communities engaging in community protocol development, stating:

⁵² *Ibid.* para. 8.

⁵³ *Ibid.* para. 8.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.* para. 8.

⁵⁵ Blog Post by E Morgera ‘Assessing the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines on benefit sharing from the use of traditional knowledge’ (2017) Online at: <https://BeneLexBeneLexblog.wordpress.com/2017/03/01/reflections-on-2016-un-biodiversity-conference-part-ii-assessing-the-mootz-kuxtal-guidelines-on-benefit-sharing-from-the-use-of-traditional-knowledge/> (Last Checked 20/08/18).

⁵⁶ Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, Para. 19.

⁵⁷ The Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity, Nagoya, 29 October 2010, In force 12 October 2014 Arts. 12 & 21(i).

“Community protocols provide communities an opportunity to focus on their development aspirations vis-a-vis their rights and to articulate for themselves and for users their understanding of their bio-cultural heritage and therefore on what basis they will engage with a variety of stakeholders. By considering the interconnections of their land rights, current socio-economic situation, environmental concerns, customary laws and traditional knowledge, communities are better placed to determine for themselves how to negotiate with a variety of actors.”⁵⁸

The Guidelines provide an overview of the possible content of community protocols including but not limited to:

“Information about:

- (a) Community identity;
- (b) Community history;
- (c) Community territoriality;
- (d) The use of culturally important practices relevant to the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity; social organization and decision-making processes (which are often collective decision-making procedures at the community level)”⁵⁹

They also contain information and ideas of community issues community protocols may address. This include conservation of biodiversity, sustainable use of plants and animal biological resources, protection of traditional knowledge, and guidance on how the various forms of FPIC can be implemented.⁶⁰ Morgera notes that IPLC representatives insisted that the Guidelines provide both information on the content of community protocols and what issues they may address.⁶¹

Morgera indicates that the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines are not intended to be the final say on the difficult questions around consent, benefit sharing and community protocols concerning use to traditional knowledge; and in fact “invited governments, relevant organisations and [IPLCs] to submit their views concerning best practiced to implement [FPIC] for consideration during the next biennium.”⁶²

This indicates two potential future outcomes. The first is the possibility of another set of principles, guidelines, or code of ethical conduct under the CBD ambit that concerns traditional knowledge and participation of IPLCs may be negotiated at a future COP. The second would be an international focus on documenting good practices under the existing guidelines, facilitated during future COPs.

5. Methodology: Language Technology and Workflow

⁵⁸ Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, Para. 19.

⁵⁹ Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, Para. 20.

⁶⁰ Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, para. 21.

⁶¹ Blog Post by E Morgera ‘Assessing the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines on benefit sharing from the use of traditional knowledge’ (2017) Online at: <https://benelexblog.wordpress.com/2017/03/01/reflections-on-2016-un-biodiversity-conference-part-ii-assessing-the-mootz-kuxtal-guidelines-on-benefit-sharing-from-the-use-of-traditional-knowledge/> (Last Checked 20/08/18).

⁶² Blog Post by E Morgera ‘Assessing the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines on benefit sharing from the use of traditional knowlegde’ (2017) Online at: <https://benelexblog.wordpress.com/2017/03/01/reflections-on-2016-un-biodiversity-conference-part-ii-assessing-the-mootz-kuxtal-guidelines-on-benefit-sharing-from-the-use-of-traditional-knowledge/> (Last Checked 20/08/18).

In the analysis of the three documents described earlier the use of language technology should serve the BENELEX research interests in a fitting and informative way. It needs to methodologically fit into the BENELEX scholarly research methods and be able to provide a contribution to addressing the BENELEX research questions. Its results should inform research where it is supplied in the workflow and it should be presented in a way that is understandable and useful for scholarly interpretation.

The approach adopted in BENELEX relies on an integration of manual evaluation and analysis from the side of the scholar on the one hand, and computer-based automatic document analysis on the other. The workflow requires a close collaboration between legal scholarly inquiry and language technology, where the overall aim of the involvement of language technology in the BENELEX activities is to support the scholarly research within the project. This support is incremental in the sense that each language technology task contributes to a scholar driven knowledge discovery in line with the research questions defined at the start of the collaboration (see section 1.2). The automatic analysis tasks have been completely in service of providing relevant information for the interpretative steps involved in the methodology of tackling the scholars' research questions.

The expectation is that this collaboration will maximize the acquisition and exploration of the conceptual structure of the domain and assist the scholar.

5.2 Methodology: General Perspective on Language Technology

Within legal artificial intelligence, language technology techniques, also called natural language processing (NLP) techniques, provide valuable text and knowledge base derived information for a wide variety of legal analysis.⁶³ NLP techniques provide a bridge between the linguistic surface structure and the underlying conceptual legal content.

Identifying, extracting, and formalizing legal knowledge remains a highly knowledge and labour-intensive task, creating a significant bottleneck between the semantic content of the source material, expressed in natural language, and computer-based, automatic use of that content. To address the bottleneck, natural language processing techniques have been applied.⁶⁴

NLP methodologies use analysis techniques such as linguistic analysis, named entity recognition, term extraction and relation extraction,⁶⁵ which provide useful information for scholarly analysis and interpretation in various stages of the research workflow. The extracted information is associated with the source texts through text metadata in the form of annotations. Knowledge is acquired semi-automatically through a collaborative effort involving language technology and legal expertise for interpretation and modelling (see the workflow in Figure 1 below).

⁶³ Azzopardi, S., Gatt, A., & Pace, G. J., Integrating Natural Language and Formal Analysis for Legal Documents: Conference Paper: Language Technologies & Digital Humanities 2016.

⁶⁴ Wyner, A. and Peters, W. (2011), On Rule Extraction from Regulations, *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications* 235
DOI 10.3233/978-1-60750-981-3-113

⁶⁵ Peters, W. and Wyner, A., Legal Text Interpretation: Identifying Hohfeldian Relations from Text. In: *Proceedings of LREC 2016*.

The inclusion of language and information technology into legal interpretation workflows customised to scholars' research questions entails a set of automated analysis tasks that assist legal scholars, and a feedback procedure between automated results and manual legal interpretation.

Research questions form the input for the work. On the basis of manual corpus analysis and evaluation of automatically extracted information these are cyclically answered, adjusted and extended based on the findings from both manual and (semi-)automatic NLP analysis. Each cycle forms an incremental progression towards the resolution of the research questions. If required, the acquired knowledge can be formalized into a data structure such as a database or ontology.

This integration of manual and automatic analysis of textual material aims at maximizing the acquisition and exploration of the conceptual structure of the legal domains. The NLP results will therefore not be a one-step solution, but will incrementally and flexibly provide textually derived information and structured knowledge within the collaborative workflow described in the previous section.

Figure 1: Collaborative automatic and manual knowledge acquisition workflow

The resulting knowledge available for subsequent scholarly exploration and interpretation, as presented in section 6, has been incrementally and collaboratively built by means of automated analysis and scholarly interpretation and evaluation.

5.3 Methodology under the BENELEX project

The BENELEX team did not concentrate on fully automatic analysis, but on a focused close reading setting that involves both automatic analysis and deep text interpretation by legal scholars with the aim of answering their research questions.

For this purpose, the team needed concepts that are pertinent to the research. These are provided as textual metadata in the form of annotations, which allows further use in text analysis and the provision of focused research material for further scholarly research.

For the creation, manipulation and presentation of text annotations that capture extracted knowledge state of the art tools such as GATE⁶⁶ (Cunningham et al., 2002) are used. Figure 2 below illustrates an annotated text in the GATE graphical user interface. Each annotation type has its own colour, with which annotated text spans are highlighted.

Also invites Parties, other Governments, relevant organizations and indigenous peoples and local communities to submit their views concerning measures to address publicly available traditional knowledge to the Executive Secretary, and requests the Executive Secretary to compile the measures and views received and make the results available for the consideration of the Working Group on Article 8(j) and Related Provisions at its tenth meeting, in order to contribute to the finalization of Tasks 7 and 12 of the revised multi-year programme of work on Article 8(j) and related provisions, as appropriate; Further invites Parties, other Governments, relevant organizations and indigenous peoples and local communities to submit their views concerning best practices to implement prior and informed consent, free, prior and informed consent or approval and involvement to the Executive Secretary, and requests the Executive Secretary, to compile the information on best practices received and make the results available for the consideration of the Working Group on Article 8(j) and Related Provisions at its tenth meeting, in order to contribute to the finalization of Tasks 7 and 12 of the revised multi-year programme of work on Article 8(j) and related provisions, as appropriate;

Figure 2: Annotations in GATE: the purple text represents instances of actors, the green text shows relevant terminology

At present, the team is targeting different texts in different sizes, which has repercussions for the selection of language technology techniques, concentrating on the relatively short documents of the Akwe: Kon Guidelines, Tkarikwaié:ri Code of Conduct and Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines. Given the data sparsity that the relatively smaller size of these documents entails, it is expected that some forms of statistical analysis will provide less reliable results. At a later stage the team will address all COPs, which stage these statistical techniques will come more to the fore.

Overall, the BENELEX methodology consists of the following main phases.

We start with **domain exploration**, which is the conceptual characterization of the domain in terms of concepts and their organization. From a methodological perspective this involves conceptual acquisition and modelling, applying manual and automatic extraction of information from the three documents described in section 4. The tasks in this conceptual exploration phase and the information resulting from this take the following forms, which are also graphically depicted in Figure 3.

Step 1: The automatic extraction of relevant keywords (terminology) and their frequency. These keywords capture the conceptual spectrum of the domain and are obtained through automatic term extraction in GATE (see section 5.4 below). The textual material we used for the extraction is the set of Cop 1-13 fragments manually selected by Parks (2018). In this way our terminology will be representative for the COP domain as a whole, and usable for studies whose COP material range will be more extensive than the three documents under consideration in this study.

Step 2: Manual close reading by scholars for the expert evaluation and selection of terms/keywords and further domain exploration. For this purpose, we make use of AntConc⁶⁷

⁶⁶ Cunningham, H., Maynard, D., Bontcheva, K. and Tablan, V. (2002), GATE: an Architecture for Development of Robust HLT Applications. In Proceedings of the 40th Annual Meeting on Association for Computational Linguistics, 7–12 July 2002, ACL '02, pages 168–175, Stroudsburg, PA, USA, 2002. Association for Computational Linguistics.

⁶⁷ <http://www.laurenceanthony.net/software/antconc/>

to enable the scholars to examine keywords in their contexts (KWIC, see section 5.4 below)⁶⁸.

Step3: The identification of entities that act as actors and stakeholders are identified as well as their typology, both manually and automatically (through named entity recognition⁶⁹ (NER) in GATE), which provides a list of persons, organizations and locations). Further, relevant actors are selected from the automatically extracted candidate terms and continuously sourced from the text during close reading.

After we have built up our domain characterization as lists of terms and actors, we then perform **contrastive comparison** between documents and actor types (step 4 in figure 3).

The terminology contained within a particular document provides it with its own semantic signature. Using this signature vocabulary and actor information, contrastive comparison between documents can highlight conceptual differences between documents (see section 5.4 below). Different documents make different statements about different actors.

The main purpose for which contrastive comparison is applied is to shed light on the different ways in which the documents talk about IPLCs. For more details see section 5.5.

Figure 3: BENELEX workflow

5.4 Phase 1: Domain Exploration

The NLP analysis is split up into different tasks. Each of these tasks has been selected for inclusion into the BENELEX workflow and yields a specific required result such as a vocabulary list or a text annotated with the metadata required for the scholarly analysis.

⁶⁸ Anthony, L. (2018). AntConc (Version 3.5.7) [Computer Software]. Tokyo, Japan: Waseda University. Available from <http://www.laurenceanthony.net/software>

⁶⁹ Azzopardi, S., Gatt, A., Pace, G. (2016), Integrating Natural Language and Formal Analysis for Legal Documents, Conference on Language Technologies & Digital Humanities, Ljubljana 2016

⁶⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Named-entity_recognition

Step 1: Term Candidate Extraction

a) Text Pre-Processing in GATE (www.gate.ac.uk)

This step is necessary to bootstrap the text analysis and assign meaningful annotations. The addition of metadata such as token, sentences and paragraphs will provide the first structural building blocks for our analysis.

Methods:

- Tokenization (partition the text into individual word or punctuation elements)
- Sentence splitting: Identify sentences
- Part of Speech tagging: assign linguistic labels such as “noun”, “plural noun”, “participle” and “past tense” to tokens.
- Paragraph detection: identify text passages that are considered thematically coherent, so it is maximally valid to assume that words that occur within the same paragraph are somehow conceptually connected.

b) Term Extraction using GATE's TermRaider

In language technology, **term extraction** is the automatic acquisition of concepts that are salient in the domain. Terms can consist of one or more words.

In general, the approach is as follows. The first step is to define patterns of part of speech information (Adjective/Noun/Preposition/Verb) combinations that form valid noun phrases in order to detect term candidates. Examples:

N "biodiversity"

NN "climate change"

AN "local community", "social benefit", "environmental protection"

NPAN "delivery of environmental benefit"

V "ban", "organize", "diversify", "strengthen"

Term candidates can also be nested inside each other, as in the following example: [[delivery] of [environmental [benefit]]]

Then frequency and other scores are derived in order to establish if the candidate string is a good candidate from a statistical point of view.

We can for instance postulate that any term candidate occurring less than 10 times in the document is to be excluded from any manual evaluation.

In our work it transpired that, given the small size of the documents, term score or frequency were not reliable enough for selecting all relevant terminology and filtering out all irrelevant candidates. Therefore, the manual evaluation took all term candidates with a frequency of greater than 2 into account.

Other scores such as TF/IDF and the domain relevance score do in the case of the three analysed documents also not provide reliable cut off thresholds for automatic term selection. Statistical information tends to become more reliable when the size of the text increases.

Step 2: Expert manual evaluation and term selection

a) Evaluation

For every evaluation task the experts were provided with extracted knowledge in the form of an Excel sheet containing a number of columns. For instance, when evaluating the term extraction, the sheet had the following columns:

Candidate term; selected (y/n); term score; frequency

for instance keyword in context (KWIC, see figure 4 below).

on Customary Sustainable Use of Biological Diversity in enabling indigenous peoples and local communities to further address biodiversity consider these sectors on these systems, Also recognizing that indigenous peoples and local communities and traditional agriculture, forestry, fisheries and all relevant stakeholders, including the business sector, and with indigenous peoples and local communities, to achieve the objectives of the Convention on Sustainable Use of Biological Diversity as well as diverse approaches undertaken by indigenous peoples and local communities in efforts to maintain genetic diversity, in a compelling and effective way to decision makers, indigenous peoples and local communities, the private sector, private landholders and appropriate, including the contributions of collective actions from indigenous peoples and local communities, of protected and other effective areas for sustainable use of biodiversity, while recognizing the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities to lands and resources; Sector-specific measures to recognize the importance of the traditional knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities for the sustainability of agriculture that in a way that provides for the needs of indigenous peoples and local communities, does not cause harm to other ecosystems; Sector-specific measures to recognize the importance of the traditional knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities, to make use of the United Nations Convention on Biodiversity, recognizing the importance of the practices of indigenous peoples and local communities and the role of natural regeneration in forest protection and invites other Governments to strengthen participation of indigenous peoples and local communities as part of a strategy for forest protection, biodiversity, and the traditional practices of sustainable use by indigenous peoples and local communities, are essential to achieving sustainable use of biodiversity and with the full and meaningful participation of indigenous peoples and local communities; 63. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 64. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 65. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 66. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 67. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 68. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 69. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 70. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 71. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 72. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 73. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 74. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 75. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 76. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 77. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 78. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 79. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 80. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 81. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 82. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 83. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 84. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 85. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 86. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 87. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 88. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 89. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 90. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 91. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 92. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 93. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 94. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 95. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 96. Also recalls decisions X/29 and XI/10, and the provision of quality jobs and income for indigenous peoples and local communities, and the need to protect it from unsustainable use; 97. Recognizes the central role of indigenous peoples and local communities in the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; 98. Also recognizes the role of the collective actions of indigenous peoples and local communities to achieve the objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity (2016). Local Biodiversity Outlooks, Indigenous Peoples' and Local Communities' Contributions to the Implementation

Figure 4: KeyWord In Context (KWIC)

Step 3: Creation of actor lists and typology of actors

a) Manual identification

During the evaluation of term candidates in step 1 the experts collected any actors they saw in the texts while examining the contexts of the term candidates. These actors were added to an incremental lookup list, which was then later used to annotate the texts with actors.

b) Named Entity Recognition (NER) in GATE

This task automatically identifies named entities such as person, organization and location, and assists the identification of actors in the three documents. Manual evaluation and selection retain valid results for the extension of the actor lists

The result is a typology of actors and a list of instances for each type. As an illustration, Figure 5 shows two GATE screenshots of elements of two lookup lists for the actor types "IPLC" and "Industry" respectively. The right-hand panes list the individual elements of the lookup lists.

All in all, lookup lists for 12 actor types have been created.

List name	Major	Minor	Language	Annotation type	Value	Feature 1	Value 1
CBD.lst	multilateralStateBody	CBDBody		Lookup	Business/private sector groups	string	Business/private sector groups
IPLCs.lst	IPLC			Lookup	Business sector	string	Business sector
academia.lst	civilSociety	academia		Lookup	Business sectors	string	Business sectors
agriculture.lst	privateSector	agriculture		Lookup	corporate donor	string	corporate donor
bodies-related-to-IPLCs.lst	IPLC	bodyRelatedToIPLC		Lookup	corporate donors	string	corporate donors
citizen-bodies.lst	civilSociety	citizenBody		Lookup	forest sector	string	forest sector
government-institutions.lst	StateInternationalOrganization	governmentInstitution		Lookup	forest sectors	string	forest sectors
industry.lst	privateSector	industry		Lookup	pension funds	string	pension funds
intergovernmental-bodies.lst	multilateralStateBody	intergovernmentalBody		Lookup	Private landowner	string	Private landowner
multilateral-state-bodies.lst	StateInternationalOrganization	multilateralStateBody		Lookup	Private landowners	string	Private landowners
ngo.lst	civilSociety	NGO		Lookup	Private sector	string	Private sector
private-institutions.lst	privateSector	privateInstitutions		Lookup	Private sectors	string	Private sectors
					Tourism industry	string	Tourism industry

List name	Major	Minor	Language	Annotation type	Value	Feature 1	Value 1
CBD.lst	multilateralStateBody	CBDBody		Lookup	Indigenous affairs	string	Indigenous affairs
IPLCs.lst	IPLC			Lookup	Indigenous and local communities	string	Indigenous and local c
academia.lst	civilSociety	academia		Lookup	Indigenous and local people	string	Indigenous and local p
agriculture.lst	privateSector	agriculture		Lookup	Indigenous group	string	Indigenous group
bodies-related-to-IPLCs.lst	IPLC	bodyRelatedToIPLC		Lookup	Indigenous peoples and local communities	string	Indigenous peoples ar
citizen-bodies.lst	civilSociety	citizenBody		Lookup	Local, traditional and technical specialists	string	Local, traditional and t
government-institutions.lst	StateInternationalOrganization	governmentInstitution		Lookup	Local and indigenous communities	string	Local and indigenous c
industry.lst	privateSector	industry		Lookup	Local and indigenous people	string	Local and indigenous p
intergovernmental-bodies.lst	multilateralStateBody	intergovernmentalBody		Lookup	Local communities	string	Local communities
multilateral-state-bodies.lst	StateInternationalOrganization	multilateralStateBody		Lookup	Local community	string	Local community
ngo.lst	civilSociety	NGO		Lookup			
private-institutions.lst	privateSector	privateInstitutions		Lookup			

Figure 5: Actor lookup lists in GATE

5.5 Summary of Phase 1: Domain Exploration

In phase 1 (step 1-3 in Figure 3) we have now collected relevant terminology and identified actor types. Figure 6 below describes the BENELEX workflow in a diagrammatic way, a summary organised around the main tasks and tools.

We now have a fully researched conceptual index that can be used in phase 2.

Figure 6: Summary of phase 1 workflow

5.6 Phase 2: Contrastive Comparison

Through **text annotation** with terminology and actor information, we can now derive the co-occurrences of these actors and terms within paragraphs. As said before, co-occurrence within paragraphs presupposes a certain level of thematic relatedness, and the inference is that co-occurring terms modulate the discourse around certain actor types.

The postulation is that the difference in terminological contexts between actor types is informative regarding the ways in which each document speaks about these actors.

In this phase the goal is to use the material developed in phase 1 to gain insight in:

- What the conceptual focus is of each document;
- How this focus is expressed in language;
- In which ways the documents differ in conceptualization;
- In which ways conceptualizations evolve and shift between these documents with different creation dates;
- How IPLCs and other actors are talked about in different documents;
- In which ways the discourse on IPCs differs from that on other actors such as Industry.

Pairwise contrastive comparison of the documents (Akwe: Kon Guidelines - Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines; Akwe: Kon Guidelines - Tkarihwaié:ri Code and Tkarihwaié:ri Code - Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines) highlights the similarities and differences between them by examining which co-occurring terms they share when mentioning IPLCs and which are unique to them.

In order to enable the experts to research these phenomena, Excel sheets were created from the text annotations that capture co-occurrence of IPLCs and terms within the same paragraph.

Terms occurring within paragraph contexts in both documents, together with their frequency
Terms unique to each document in the pair with their frequency

The experts then use this contrastive information to make observations, the results of which are discussed in section 6 below.

It needs to be borne in mind that the scope of our findings is influenced by the size of the text analysed in this pilot. Phase 1 above was performed over all COP documents up to and including 2013 (960,000 word tokens).

Phase 2 as described above involved the analysis of three documents totalling 15,500-word tokens. Statistical analysis becomes more representative and reliable when used on large amounts of text. Therefore, the analysis of significant context patterns in phase 2 is limited by the size of the texts involved.

6. Research Outcomes

This section outlines the initial observations of our comparative study on the evolution of language between the Akwé: Kon Guidelines (2004), the Tkarihwaié:ri Ethical Code (2010), and Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines (2016).

6.1 Shared Terms

Traditional knowledge

The term “traditional knowledge” is the most frequent shared term between all three documents. This is unsurprising, since the whole treaty basis of the inclusion of IPLCs in the CBD is on the basis of their traditional knowledge useful for the conservation of biodiversity.

Local community, indigenous people, indigenous peoples and local communities

The term “local community” is much more frequently used in the Akwe: Kon Guidelines, while “indigenous people” appears only once. In the Tkarihwaié:ri Code, these terms are less frequent, appearing 5 and 2 times respectively. In the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, “local community” and “indigenous people” appear nearly equal amounts of times (40 and 38). This reflects the evolutionary nature of the CBD, which used the term ‘indigenous and local communities’ until the adoption of the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines in 2014. At COP 12 in 2014, the term ‘indigenous peoples and local communities’ began to be used.⁷⁰ This is why the Akwe: Kon Guidelines use 82 times the term “indigenous and local communities”, and in the Tkarihwaié:ri Code, this appears as the most frequent term (69 times), while in the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines this term occurs only once.

The story of the politics behind the CBD’s move towards the use of the term ‘indigenous peoples’ is a long one. The original reluctance to use the term stemmed from States that saw the word ‘peoples’ as implying an admission of the need to recognise particular rights to a group. This was confirmed at the international level with the language of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), which links the term firmly to the recognition of the right to self-determination for these groups, including rights over natural resources. Some Parties to the CBD were nervous about reproducing this language of self-determination due to potential secessionist ambitions of peoples within their borders. Others saw a difficulty in reproducing the language of UNDRIP because the CBD specifically recognises the sovereignty of States over their natural resources. The language of UNDRIP could be construed as a challenge to this. When the decision to endorse UNDRIP and adopt the term ‘indigenous peoples’ in the CBD was finally taken in 2014, the term was used in the formula ‘indigenous peoples and local communities’. Here, the political meaning of the word ‘peoples’ is arguably diluted by the equation of indigenous peoples with all other types of local communities. While the intention of the CBD may be to refer to the idea that both of these groups make contributions to biodiversity conservation and sustainable use, some commentators have taken a wider reading of the terms as highlighting the idea of the marginalisation of both groups, since marginalisation is very much linked to the definition of indigenous peoples in UNDRIP. It has also been argued that the combined expression simultaneously denies any unique position to indigenous peoples, undermining the link with claims for rights.⁷¹

The analysis of the terms in the three different texts examined here thus takes on further potential meaning. As expected, the formulation ‘indigenous and local communities’ dominates in both the Akwe: Kon Guidelines and the Tkarihwaié:ri Code. As noted above, the term appears only once in the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, replaced instead with the combination ‘indigenous peoples and local communities’, with the first use accompanied by a footnote referring to the COP decision discussing the use of the term. The completeness of the move to use the word ‘indigenous peoples’ is thus reflected in the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines.

⁷⁰ CBD Decision XII/12 F (2014).

⁷¹ Harry Jonas, Jael Makagon, and Holly Shrumm, (2013) *The Living Convention: a compendium of internationally recognised rights that support the integrity and resilience of indigenous peoples’ and local communities’ territories and other social-ecological systems* (Natural Justice, 2013).

Indeed, the guidelines were discussed extensively at the CBD *Ad Hoc Open-ended Working Group on Article 8(j)*, where representatives of IPLCs have a noteworthy presence, and the overlap between the Working Group's recommendations and the text adopted at the COP has also been noted.⁷² Overall, this difference in terminology between the first two sets of guidelines and the third indicates a more general shift taking place – further research is needed to determine how quickly this shift took place after the 2012 decision.

Customary Law

Both the Akwe: Kon and the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines use with similar frequency the term customary law: this may indicate that customary law is seen to play a role in local-level processes in the eyes of CBD Parties. However, the term customary law occurs only once in the Tkarihwaí:ri guidelines. This could simply be due to the short length of the document, and that Paragraph 4 specifies that it is the right of IPLCs, according to their customary law and procedures, to identify the relevant holders of their traditional knowledge, thus giving a general applicability of customary law to the rest of the guidelines.⁷³ In addition, the subject matter of the Akwe: Kon and Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines, on impact assessment and PIC respectively, is perhaps more clearly tied to customary law which may provide guidance on how indigenous peoples and local communities should be involved and consulted, through which bodies and mechanisms, and where particular areas of cultural importance lie.

In this vein, Tobin discusses the need for the respect and recognition of customary law more generally for the protection of indigenous peoples' knowledge and resource rights.⁷⁴ Vermeulen, on the other hand, points to the difficulties encountered at regional and national levels when legal pluralism comes to be practiced, underlining the rigidity of some legal systems with regards to oral histories as evidence and collectively held knowledge for example.⁷⁵ It is important to recognise that legal pluralism is controversial. Most national legal systems are strict as to when and how they allow application of customary law, in other words, most legal systems are not pluralistic in the first place. This may explain CBD Parties' reluctance to commit to such application in an international legal document. As such, this could indicate a reason for a general shying away from the inclusion of the term customary law in the CBD text itself. At the same time, it may also provide some evidence that the points of view of representatives of IPLCs were included to a greater extent in the guidelines examined here, as the interest for this group in including the term is clear, while the reluctance for Parties may lie in the kinds of complications discussed by Vermeulen. Further research will hopefully shed more light on this.

FPIC

⁷² Blog Post by E Morgera 'Assessing the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines on benefit sharing from the use of traditional knowledge' (2017) Online at: <https://BENELEXblog.wordpress.com/2017/03/01/reflections-on-2016-un-biodiversity-conference-part-ii-assessing-the-mootz-kuxtal-guidelines-on-benefit-sharing-from-the-use-of-traditional-knowledge/> (Last Checked 20/08/18).

⁷³ Tkarihwaí:ri Code of Conduct, Para. 4.

⁷⁴ B M Tobin, 'Bridging the Nagoya compliance gap: The fundamental role of customary law in protection of indigenous peoples' resource and knowledge rights' *9/2 Law, Environment and Development Journal* (2013) 142

⁷⁵ S Vermeulen, 'The Nagoya protocol and customary law: The paradox of narratives in the law' *9/2 Law, Environment and Development Journal* (2013), 185

Another notable difference is in the idea of ‘informed consent’. The differences here cannot be attributed to the different subject matters dealt with in the three documents:

- Akwe: Kon Guidelines deals with ESCIA;
- Tkarihwaié:ri Code deals with research involving IPLCs knowledge or activities;
- Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines deal with prior informed consent;

The concept of FPIC is central to all of these areas. Though we would expect more mentions of this in Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines as their core subject matter, this difference (8 in Akwe: Kon Guidelines, 1 in Tkarihwaié:ri Code, 40 in Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines) is perhaps greater than one would have expected given the differences in length (Akwe: Kon Guidelines longer, Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines shorter, Tkarihwaié:ri Code shortest). The high number of mentions in the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines may provide the key to understanding the meaning of this difference.

The discussions between representatives of indigenous peoples and local communities at the *Ad Hoc* Working Group on Article 8(j) that preceded the COP which adopted these guidelines hosted debates about the different meanings attributed to the idea of informed consent, which are illustrated in its rather lengthy title which states that the guidelines seek ‘to ensure the “prior and informed consent”, “free, prior and informed consent” or “approval and involvement”, depending on national circumstances, of indigenous peoples and local communities’. As this title suggests, debates about the extent and manner of the involvement of IPLCs in decisions about activities involving their cultural and intellectual heritage were not resolved at this time. The word ‘free’ in particular was debated, and seen as an addition that would imply more than simple non-coercion, but a duty in terms of designing culturally appropriate consultation procedures sensitive to issues such as timing, language, the provision of information in appropriate formats and the like. Though not as politically loaded as the discussion of ‘indigenous peoples’ outlined above, the resulting guidelines ended up using a number of different terms when referring to the general idea of informed consent. The lengthy formulation of these terms means that our methodology picks up on the initial term, informed consent, yet closer examination reveals that the longer list is used throughout the document. This indicates that this is an area where the terminology is far from settled in the CBD arena. Two possible readings of this finding can be suggested. First, it may be that the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines re-open a question about FPIC that appeared to be answered in the earlier Akwe: Kon Guidelines. Though the Akwe: Kon Guidelines use the term prior informed consent, without the preceding ‘free’, it is unequivocal that prior informed consent must be gained – not merely an alternative to ‘approval’ and ‘involvement’. In the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, this question could be read as being reopened in the sense that the long list of terms used throughout range from stronger formulations preferred by groups representing indigenous peoples and local communities (i.e. *free* prior and informed consent) to weaker formulations of approval and involvement. On the other hand, we could also see the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines as a forum that opens up a debate about what the detail of informed consent should contain – such as when it should be gained, what will happen if it is denied, and how culturally sensitive and flexible to local circumstances actors seeking consent must be. This idea of a debate underway is confirmed by a similar asymmetry between the shared term ‘involvement’ – 5 in Akwe: Kon Guidelines, 3 in Tkarihwaié:ri Code, 21 in Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines.

Innovation and Development

Terms like ‘innovation’ and ‘development’ are much more common in the Akwe: Kon Guidelines and the Tkarihawié:ri Code than in the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, which suggests several possible readings. Innovation and development may be linked purely to the projects that would trigger the need for an impact assessment – certainly they are both words more generally linked with the language of market economics. On the other hand, since this analysis looks specifically at terms closely linked to indigenous peoples and local communities as a specific actor type within the CBD, their use may indicate a clearer link to the idea of IPLCs being important insofar as they contribute to biodiversity and allow innovations and development to occur, a theme that is less central in the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines. A plausible argument explaining this is thus that the use of terminology is related to the subject matter of the two instruments: the Akwé: Kon Guidelines relate to developments, while the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines relate to the use of traditional knowledge, rather than the effectiveness of participation by IPLCs. This is bolstered by work discussing the key inputs from indigenous peoples and local communities’ representatives prior to the adoption of both texts. According to reports from the *Ad Hoc* Working Group on Article 8(j) meeting, that negotiated and adopted the Akwé: Kon Guidelines in 2003, representatives from IPLCs were in full-force.⁷⁶ For example, the meeting officially began with an indigenous opening ceremony, UNEP representative Nehemiah Rotich called for the full and effective participation of IPLCs at all levels and in all sectors of society, and IPLC representatives were given equal-footing with States Parties during the negotiations.⁷⁷ As for the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines, the *Ad Hoc* Working Group on Article 8(j) was also noted to have played a key role in terms of providing input – texts suggested by indigenous peoples and local communities’ representatives and backed by State parties were included in the final text of the guidelines.⁷⁸

Culture and Heritage

While the Akwe: Kon Guidelines scored higher for more market-oriented terminology, this is accompanied by higher scores for terms including ‘cultural’ and ‘heritage’, which are areas where impacts must be taken into account in assessment procedures. The very fact that these areas are considered shows a move to tie market considerations with questions of culture and heritage in the CBD. In itself, this signals an understanding of the inextricable link between indigenous peoples and local communities’ roles in conserving biodiversity and their cultures and heritage. Reading into this from a more political point of view, it may also be evidence to suggest that the strategy of using the CBD arena as an initial platform for pushing wider agendas linked to rights and self-determination (where some groups are concerned) is bearing fruit. While the CBD retains its interest through language more centred on the market, these are conditional on impact assessments to ensure respect of themes of more central interest to IPLCs. ‘Cultural’ and ‘cultural and intellectual heritage’ also appear frequently in the Tkarihawié:ri Code, as it concerns respect for the cultural and intellectual heritage of indigenous local communities regarding research on their traditional knowledge and activities. A similar type of interpretation can also apply here as that outlined for the Akwe: Kon Guidelines. This type of language is rare in the Mo’otz Kuxtal Guidelines. This seems to

⁷⁶ See Earth Negotiation Bulletin ‘Summary of the third meeting of the *ad hoc* open-ended inter-sessional working group on Article 8(j) and related provisions of the Convention on Biological Diversity’ Vol. 09 No. 273 <http://enb.iisd.org/vol09/enb09273e.html>

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*

⁷⁸ Morgera blog post on Mo’otz Kuxtal

support the second interpretation of the Guidelines outlined above, which frames the reopening of the debate around free, prior and informed consent as a challenge to gains made by IPLCs.

Benefit Sharing & Community Protocols

The Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines score the highest number of references to 'equitable sharing of benefits' (11 vs. 1 vs. 1), while the term 'benefit-sharing' also occurs 12 times in the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines but not at all in the Akwe: Kon Guidelines, and only once in the Tkarihawié:ri Code. This suggests the evolution of the understanding of benefit-sharing and its close links to the themes of involvement and consultation. It can also be explained in terms of context by the fact that the Akwé: Kon Guidelines focus on prior informed consent, as opposed to benefit sharing. The importance of community protocols has been recognised by CBD Parties through the introduction of the concept in the Nagoya Protocol on benefit sharing arising out of the utilization of traditional knowledge.⁷⁹ The use of the term 'community protocol' in the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines provides greater substance to the idea of the role of paying close attention to what communities want and need in terms of defining benefits arising from the use of traditional knowledge. Further, it suggests that these texts are more preoccupied with getting a fairer deal for IPLCs, even if development and innovation are not so present. The fact that 'community protocols' are only mentioned in the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines also adds to this view.

General observations on the evolution of language and unique terms

There is what could be termed a simpler instrumental view of IPLCs because of their contribution to biodiversity protection prior to the Nagoya Protocol, where the CBD objective of benefit-sharing is expanded upon. After the adoption of the Nagoya Protocol, the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines flesh out some points within the Nagoya Protocol around the central role of PIC for benefit sharing. Overall, this hints at a view of IPLCs as a group that should be treated more fairly regardless of their contributions to the protection of biodiversity – at least in a layperson's understanding of such language. The legal reasoning for the inclusion of IPLCs in the CBD remains clearly rooted in their roles as protectors of biodiversity within wider ecosystems, and in their roles as right-holders over their territories, traditional knowledge, and genetic resources. Nevertheless, there is still scope to suggest that while earlier guidelines are more explicit in underlining the roots of the position of IPLCs, the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines expand the rights-centred view of IPLCs' positions by using more legal terms, including 'unlawful appropriation', 'technology transfer', 'compliance', 'rights of indigenous peoples and local communities', and 'non-monetary benefit'.⁸⁰ This would suggest that in some areas of the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines, IPLCs have pursued a strategy to bring language more in line with a wider political agenda, albeit without affecting the legal interpretation and application of the Convention. Thus, the implicit suggestion is read in the view of a political strategy by IPLCs to use the CBD arena as a springboard to push evolution and innovation in their favour also in other arenas.⁸¹ IPLCs may be acting politically here, as a historically marginalised set of groups who consider themselves as deserving rights beyond

⁷⁹ Nagoya Protocol, Arts. 12, 21(i)

⁸⁰ This idea is also reflected in the importance of language that emphasizes the CBD's recognition of the importance of traditional knowledge and customary sustainable use. See Parks (n 4).

⁸¹ See e.g. D F Robinson *Biodiversity, Access and Benefit-Sharing – Global Case Studies* (2015) Abingdon: Routledge.

any contribution made in terms of biodiversity protection or as owners of certain information or lands.

This idea of an implicit evolution in the language of the CBD from a more instrumental or more bureaucratic view of IPLCs towards a more independent group of rights-holders is also suggested by the more technical content of the terms unique to the Akwe: Kon Guidelines, including in its full title and subject matter ('sacred site', variations on 'impact assessment', 'possible impact', 'proposed development' etc.). The terms associated with IPLCs' participation is also telling in this respect. In the Akwe: Kon Guidelines, common terms include 'consultation', 'public consultation', and 'stakeholder'. In the Tkarihawié:ri Code these terms evolve towards a different type of language linked more clearly to the questions of why participation is needed – 'ethical conduct', 'respect', 'sacred sites and species', etc. In the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines, the emphasis in terms seems to shift to the theme of making participation 'effective', also invoking 'trust'. Overall, this also signals an evolution from a rather bureaucratic view of IPLC involvement as 'consultation' which indicates listening but not being bound to actually do anything about the views of others, through to an emphasis on ethics, also accompanied by language recognising the faults of colonialism (repatriation, recovery of traditional knowledge), through to the current situation where the effort seems to be on giving real meaning to IPLC participation as distinct from mere consultation. A final point in this direction is the view that the unique language of the Akwe: Kon Guidelines suggests that as long as an impact assessment is carried out, a development will and should take place. The terms in the document indicate safeguards, grievance measures and the like, but nothing clearly denotes the possibility of denying permission. This seems to contrast with the recognition of fault in the Tkarihawié:ri Code, but as detailed above that recognition of wrongdoing seems firmly planted in a colonial past and few terms appear to recognise the continuing post- or neo-colonial present. This does seem to come more to the fore in the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines, with their unique terms constructing a more concrete view of the current rights and grievances of IPLCs.

A frame analysis of COP decision texts referring to participation by IPLCs also bolsters the view of a discourse evolving from a more bureaucratic and formal view towards a wider debate about how to make participation effective. Specifically, the frame analysis indicated that the content of 'participation' is very far from settled in the CBD - language is often vague and fails to identify specific roles for specific actors. Nevertheless, in more recent decisions new frames around themes including 'participation for respect', which refers to texts that see the role of participation as contributing to the actorhood of IPLCs as rights-holders, have emerged⁸² (Parks and Schröder 2018).

6.1 Research Material

An appendix containing the research material produced, together with a description of the data is available on the BENELEX project website⁸³. The appendix also contains additional material derived from the full COP 1-13 texts, usable for future extension of this research.

7. Conclusion

⁸²L Parks & M Schroeder 'What we talk about when we talk about 'local' participation in international biodiversity law. The changing scope of Indigenous peoples and local communities' participation under the Convention on Biological Diversity' 11 *Participation and Conflict* (2018) 743-785.

⁸³ <https://www.strath.ac.uk/research/strathclydecentreenvironmentallawgovernance/benelex/>

In this paper, we illustrated a method for using language technology to analyse legal texts. Our interest within the BENELEX project was in following up in-depth qualitative research on the discourses about indigenous peoples and local communities in the Convention on Biological Diversity, and about participation by these groups in particular. Our long-term aim is to carry out analyses of all CBD COP decisions (totalling 960,000 word tokens) to determine whether or not a distinct discourse about indigenous peoples and local communities (as opposed to other actors) exists and, if so, how those discourses differ. This paper presents a first step in this direction – an initial comparison between three documents that are key to understanding the evolution of discourses about the participation of indigenous peoples and local communities: the Akwé: Kon Guidelines, the Tkarihawié:ri Code of Ethical Conduct, and the Mo'otz Kuxtal Guidelines. These documents (containing 15,500 word tokens) can be considered as key points that provide concise summaries of lengthy debates about the role and participation of these groups within the CBD. By comparing these three documents, we were able to draw conclusions about the overall evolution of the discourse about IPLCs and their participation that could easily be verified on the basis of specialist knowledge held by other members of the BENELEX research team. In this sense the analysis discussed here is intended as a 'test' of our method before rolling it out to CBD COP decisions as a whole. The other purpose of the analysis was to generate new research questions and avenues for our future work.

In terms of its function as a test, the analysis did not raise any major surprises for the research team. This is encouraging since it signals that the method works, and could safely be applied to larger amounts of text that cannot be manually compared. Legal informatics, when, as in our pilot, combined with manual and close reading-based methods, is a useful tool for scholarly analysis because it allows focused access to information contained within larger volumes of text. This access is customized to and directed by the research questions. Legal informatics informs these research questions and produces analysis results that scholars then can use for their reformulation.

The results of the comparison of three well-known texts would also, we hoped, indicate directions for future research. First, the findings from this small-scale comparison suggest that there may be a re-opening of the debate about what 'consultation' and related terms mean within the CBD and, more broadly, what 'participation' by indigenous peoples and local communities means. This is one avenue that can be explored in the larger scale analyses, through close attention to the meanings and actors linked to consultation, free, prior and informed consent and related terms, and participation. The changing language or synonyms for these could provide further insights about whether this debate has opened up once more, and give more information on its content.

A second avenue suggested by these small-scale results concerns the terms associated with a market discourse, such as 'innovation' and 'development', found to be linked to indigenous peoples and local communities in the earlier Akwé: Kon Guidelines, but to be replaced with language more linked to discourses recognising other worldviews in later texts. This interesting evolution could be further explored in a larger scale analysis. For example, is there any evidence of diffusion of these terms from discussions related to more obviously economic actors (industry) into discussions about IPLCs? And in the opposite direction, is there any diffusion of terms related to the rights of IPLCs into discussions about economic actors, industry, or indeed State actors?

A third avenue concerns the emergence of language linked to indigenous peoples and local communities' rights in later documents. Further analysis could furnish clearer evidence about this, and answer similar questions about diffusion to or from other types of actors, and the role of States.

The value added of this larger-scale analysis is not to draw conclusions about legal implications – on the question of rights, for example, the CBD clearly has not reflected more directly IPLCs' legal rights. Yet it can be argued that political bases for right claims can be discerned in the texts of CBD COP decisions, and some have been used by international courts.⁸⁴ It is a method that can provide information for scholars of the politics of environmental decision-making forums, as well as socio-legal scholars more generally, thus adding to the existing legal literature on the CBD, as well as socio-legal scholarship that focuses on the treaty text or specific policies. What legal informatics can bring to the table when combined with manual and close reading-based methods is precisely the possibility of drawing conclusions about the general shape of evolutions in discourses over time on the basis of large amounts of text. It is this that can inform research questions of interest to scholars of the politics of environmental decision-making forums, as well as socio-legal scholars more generally, by indicating the general shapes of discourses around certain actors or groups of actors and informing us about the roles and themes most often linked with these actors. It can also tell us about gaps in discourse and possibilities for future evolutions.

⁸⁴ E Morgera, 'Under the radar: The role of fair and equitable benefit-sharing in protecting and realizing human rights connected to natural resources' BENELEX Working Paper N. 10 (rev October 2010).